

A Model of Creative Community Development in Khon Kaen: Buea-Ban (Old City Pillar Shrine)

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: February 24, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: April 27, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Creative Community, Development Model, Khon Kaen Province, Thailand</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4723778</p>	<p><i>Community development is a type of development that is unique in its own way, philosophies, concepts, principles and practices based on originality. The development is the process of educating people to develop knowledge ideas to gain potential of self-sufficiency. This is consistent with the first national strategy of Thailand to achieve the vision 'Thailand is stable, prosperous and sustainable, is a developed country in accordance with the philosophy of sufficiency economy'. To meet with the mentioned national goal and in support of the National Research Council of Thailand, this research aims to develop a creative community model: Old City Pillar Shrine (Buea-Ban) in Khon Kaen Province. Participants (N=66), chosen by Purposive Sampling consisted of representatives of Khon Kaen Municipality, local scholars, representatives of 'Hoop-Taem' Club, KhonKaen Club. Tools used in this study included Interviews and Focus Group Discussion. The data was analysed using the Descriptive Content Analysis. The result of the research leads to the acquisition of the Creative Community Model called 'KIDPU Model' consisting of 1) K: Knowledge Management; 2) I: Identity (reflection of identity); 3) D: Development; 4) P: Publication and 5) U: Utilization.</i></p>

Introduction

Nowadays, conservation, localization and global trends can go hand in hand and coincide with the participation process of local dwellers who own the area and reflect the local character including the identity of society until becoming a city with a clear identity. The factors related to the creative city are: people, place and identity. The factors related to the creative city led to the development of the creative city concept in creating an environment and public activities conducive to learning of local people, relying on important elements like 'Creative thinking', the key factor that connects society, culture, environment and industries (Nantanit Somkid & Phrasuthirattanapandit, 2019). Over the past 40 years of national development, the economy at the forefront of economic growth as a measure (GDP), has created an increasing income gap between the poor and the rich. The Gross Domestic Happiness (GDH) is an issue that people start to address and call for reinstatement as the main or goal of local community development. The direction of urban development and local development in the 21st century is urban development that values humanity because it is the most important asset and the main engine of the city and local economy. Local people and culture play an important role in making cities a space for creativity building dynamism in urban society. So, the factors in the development of creative cities are made up of multi-sectoral cooperation both government and private agencies in order for local communities to be able to manage themselves. Also, the community must have confidence in the potential of the people and is able to manage themselves by adhering to the principle of self-sufficiency (Nantanit Somkid & Phrasuthirattanapandit, 2019).

In Thailand, the 20-Year National Strategy (2018-1980), which is the first national strategy of Thailand according to the Constitution of the Kingdom of Thailand, must be put into practice to achieve the vision of Thailand to be a stable, prosperous, and sustainable developed country utilizing the philosophy of sufficiency economy. The National Strategy on Human Resource Development and Enhancement focuses on developing and upgrading people of all ages in all dimensions to become good, competent, and quality human resources (Office of the National Economic and Social Development Council, 2020). Community development is a type of development with its unique philosophies, concepts, principles, and practices. Sometimes, it is recognized as a process of educating people to develop knowledge and ideas to have potential and self-reliance in all areas (Jiraphan Kanchanachitra, 1990).

Khon Kaen Province is an important city and a centre of various aspects of the Northeast, causing a systematic and continuous development in terms of education, trade and services, finance, medicine, industry, transport, and logistics in the upper northeastern region. In response to the national vision and support of the National Research Council of Thailand, the researchers were interested in researching ways to develop Khon Kaen as a

creative community. In so doing, this research had its aim to create the creative community development model (CCD Model): Old City Pillar Shrine (Buea-Ban), Khon Kaen Province based on the local and religious culture.

Objectives& Methodology

This action research aimed at developing a CCD Model: Buea-Ban in Khon Kaen Province and it was carried out using a mixed research method. The implementation of research on CCD Model: Buea-Ban, Khon Kaen Province was divided into 3 phases. Phase 1: Organize a meeting of the 66 research participants to review development guidelines; Phase 2: Design the creative community based on opinions of representatives of Khon Kaen Municipality, local scholars, representatives of 'Hoop-Taem' Club, KhonKaen Club; Phase 3: Develop Buea-Ban in Khon Kaen Province in collaboration with communities and related agencies to support the learning of people in Khon Kaen.

Results

Development of CCD Model: Buea- Ban

The development of a creative community can be achieved through cooperation and the joint ideas from the community and factors that exist within the community combined with the use of modern technology. In this stage, the research team has a clear goal to make the most of the community's benefits in terms of 1) understanding, 2) accessing, 3) developing, and 4) using the information of a creative community as illustrated.

Illustration 3: the goals of the Khon Kaen creativecity development

For developing a creative community, in all activities, the research team have asked for cooperation of the community chair, community representatives, villagers, 'Hoop Team' Club, Khon Kaen Municipality, private entities to think, do, and join in solving problems. Therefore, the study can carry out various activities successfully and the form of activities that contribute to the development of a creative community are shown in the illustration below.

2) Dissemination of research results (Publication)

In the publication of this research results, the research team's goal is 'to return information to the community' to promote and encourage people in the community to have the knowledge and an understanding of the rationale of research consistent with reality and society. This time, researchers have disseminated the research results in 2 formats as follows:

- 2.1) Opening a forum for villagers;
- 2.2) Broadcasting through television and radio stations (NBT).

Figure 5: the opening ceremony of the forum and dissemination of research results

3) Utilization of research results

3.1 Policy utilization: the results of policy research is used to create the Municipal Law or Policies of Khon Kaen Municipality.

3.2 Academic use: it is the use of research results for teaching and learning about the history of Khon Kaen Province. This leads to learning and creating learning materials on history of the city of Khon Kaen, history of Buea-Ban, culture and arts and traditions of Khon Kaen. For this research, researchers have created knowledge in six topics; each subject has a QR code that can be scanned to obtain the information of each topic. This reduces time to find the stories of the history of Buea-Ban for visitors.

3.3 Public use: this research has benefited the people in term of improving the quality of life and people's economy, including arts and culture and sufficiency economy lifestyle, etc. The research team has created innovations: 1) intelligent electric poles; 2) signs on the old city pillar; 3) signs of Buea-Ban on the road surface in the middle of the city at the entrance of Buea-Ban; 4) painting on the road surface on the entrance of Buea-Ban; 5) landscape improvement of Buea-Ban both inside; 6) establishing a check-in point to bring the information of Buea-Ban on the map (Google Maps) of Thailand which can be searched easily.

3.4 Spatial application: introduction of research results to six communities, including Wat That Community, Wat Klang Community, Nong Waeng Community 1, Nong Waeng Community 2, Nong Waeng Community 3, and Nong Waeng Community 4 in Khon Kaen Province.

3.5 Indirect use: it is the creation of mental value, raising the mind, creating aesthetics and happiness for the people in the community.

Discussion

1) Creative Community Development: the development of a creative community comes from community cooperation, ideas and factors within the community, combined with the appropriate use of modern technology. For developing from the actual community area, the development should be started from Buea-Ban, the focal point of Khon Kaen people. It is an area that has long been a priority for the public and in need to develop in conjunction with the development of modern technology in order for people to easily access and find information. This is consistent with the work of Wannatham Kanjanasuwan (2010), 'Strong Community Management Process: Forms, Factors and Indicators' which indicated seven critical management processes of the strong community development: (1) community participation; (2) exchange of knowledge; (3) process of building and rebuilding; (4) process for exercising community rights; (5) community decision-making process; (6) network development and (7) self-management. Besides, the indicators for building strong community are divided into four components: economic dimension, dimensions of society and community organization, dimensions of culture, learning, and dimensions of natural resources and environment.

2) The goal of public relations is 'returning information to the community' to promote and encourage people in the community to logically find knowledge and an understanding of Buea-Ban in consistence with nature and social responsibility. In this research, the public relations have been organized by two forms: organizing a forum of villagers and broadcasting on the radio and television station of Thailand (NBT), and disseminating it online. This is conformed with the study of Nantaporn Adirekchotikul and Ketsarin Chokpermpoon (2018) 'The Development of Tourism Public Relations in Maklua Mai Subdistrict Administrative Organization, Maklua Mai Subdistrict, Sungnoen District, Nakhon Ratchasima', and its result found that the community required the Subdistrict Administrative Organization to publicize through the website and add information content of tourist

attractions; souvenirs should have a foreign language, be promoted on website and product banners should show the uniqueness of the tourist attraction. This result included giving the opportunity for the community to participate in the preparation of tourism publicity. This is consistent with the study of Nuntipa Pushsapavardhana and Nawin Wongsomboon (2020), demonstrating that the most reliable media in providing information are human and internet. Tourists have expectations about the style, personnel, content and public relations media. Therefore, the quantitative research showed visitors receive the most information from individual media, it is imperative that the public relations should be promoted through the visitors to create impression in service. The public relation is also made by using personal communication of journalists or other writers. This is also consistent with the research results of Kultip Sastrarut and Thanakarn Duangratana (2014) 'Communication campaigning in urban health areas in the dimension of communication for social responsibility' which mentions that communication for social responsibility is a communication process through the external dimension of the educational organization that Dhurakij Pongthong University has carried out activities in the form of a campaign communication project in correction and development of society through media, activities under the project 'River from stream to mother'. This reflects that educational organizations have played a role as an educational leader in creating a social change in a way, which uses the strengths of a university that has a Faculty of Communication Arts to create a faculty project to allow the faculty and students to participate in the process of communication with the community. This leads to creating a good image (Corporate Citizenship), which is the cornerstone of building the trust and value of the university in the consumer's point of view. In this regard, researchers emphasize the CSR communication elements in the area of community development (Community Involvement and Development) through media. These activities are consisted of three elements: (1) organization, the message sender; (2) the stakeholders, the message receivers, (3) image or message.

3) Mutual Use: this research is action research with a process to engage the community and those involved in all activities to develop areas to support the learning of the community. The community is therefore directly affected by (1) policy utilization: it is the utilization of policy research results in the actual implementation by using as information to create the Municipal Law or Policies of the Khon Kaen Municipality; (2) academic benefit: it is the use of research results for teaching the history of Khon Kaen Province. This leads to learning on creating learning materials on history of the city of Khon Kaen and Buea-Ban; (3) public use: this research has benefited the people to improve the quality of life and the economy, including the use of arts and culture, sufficiency economy lifestyle, etc. in their life; 4) spatial benefit: it is the introduction of research results to use in a specific area, i.e., Khon Kaen Municipality and at least six communities; 5) indirect use: it is the creation of mental value and aesthetics creating happiness for people in the community. To further development the mutual use of the research finding, there are three suggested methods. First, it is important to create the interaction between government agencies and the research community to disseminate research results into utilization. This is consistent with the research of Phakpoom Tippakoon (2018), studying the factors affecting the use of research by Thai government agencies. The research demonstrated that if the government wants to use the research result more in policy, it must establish a connection mechanism between government and research sectors to allow exchange and learning between each other. Currently, some research funding agencies have focused on creating connections between researchers and users of research results throughout the research process. However, until now, there has not been a systematic assessment of the said approach effective in terms of increasing utilization levels. The second is to motivate researchers to drive the research results towards policy utilization. It could be said that currently there is no a concrete system to attract researchers put their work to be used. Even in the assessment of the educational quality of higher education institutions, there is an indicator for the use of research results but it does not lead the individual inspiration to bring the research results in use. Therefore, the inspiration system in use of the research results should be designed to allow researchers to see the benefits of their investment in driving research into policy utilization. Third, the need for agencies to use the research results is one of the most important factors of utilization of the research outcomes. The key point is to know the need of government agencies in using research outcomes. At this point, if there is a mechanism that continuously links information between government agencies and researchers on the regular basis. This will benefit both government agencies and researchers in developing the research in the future.

Recommendations

1) Recommendations at the policy level

The administrators or stakeholders should promote the development of a creative community model based on the factors existing within the community in order to create pride in the people in the community so that people become conscious of their love for their hometown and recognize a learning area within that community.

2) Suggestions for applying research results

Stakeholders should apply a CCD Model discovered in this research to develop the community as a cultural tourism destination to create stability, wealth, and sustainability for the community.

3) Suggestions for the subsequent research

There should be a study of the development of cultural tourism areas to create sustainability for people within the community based on government policy. Also, there should be a study on the factors contributing to the success of cultural tourism in each location, both in administration and management, based on cooperation from all related sectors.

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